

Results of Single Event Effect Testing at the New HEARTS@CERN High-Energy Heavy Ion Facility at CERN

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Abstract—We present results for SEU, SEL and SEB testing of several electronic devices under high-energy heavy ion irradiation at the new HEARTS@CERN facility at CERN.

I. INTRODUCTION

HIGH-energy heavy ions (> 100 MeV/n) are expected to become instrumental to achieve radiation effects testing of state-of-the-art commercial devices characterized by increased complexity. They can ensure sufficiently high and constant linear energy transfer (LET) over ranges exceeding several hundreds of microns. Thus, it becomes possible to test devices without removing their packages and without reliance on vacuum chambers. This can save on test preparation efforts and costs related to delidding and thinning of the substrate of, e.g., flip-chips.

The high-energy heavy ion capability for radiation effects testing of electronics in Europe is going to be tremendously increased by 2027 thanks to the HEARTS EU project. This project aims at developing high-energy heavy ion capabilities that satisfy the requirements for radiation effects testing of the space industry. The infrastructures are being developed at CERN and GSI.

In October 2023, CERN arranged a two weeks irradiation campaign at the Proton Synchrotron (PS) East Experimental Area (EA) with Pb beams. The irradiation campaign was largely devoted to the setting up of the beam properties as well as to the calibration of the dosimetry instrumentation. The final part of this run was used to perform single-event effects (SEE) measurements on a number of devices. These tests included single-event upsets (SEU) measurements on memory devices, single-event latchup (SEL) measurements on memory devices and single-event burnout (SEB) measurements on power MOSFETs.

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II. FACILITY DESCRIPTION

The experimental area exploited in 2023 makes use of the well known CHARM mixed-field irradiation area [1,2] at CERN. This area is served by the PS, a synchrotron that is capable of accelerating protons up to 24 GeV and high Z ions, such as Pb, up to 5 GeV/n. This facility has been exploited for this kind of tests since 2017 [3,4] and, as of 2021, has undergone significant upgrades to expand the previously limited capabilities of the facility, mainly in terms of ion beam LET. This was firstly enabled by the European Space Agency initiative (project known as CHIMERA) [5] and, later, by the financing from the EU.

Under the configurations studied and developed during October 2023, the PS was set to accelerate Pb ions in an energy range of 0.65-2.7 GeV/n. The ions extracted from the accelerator are transported through a 130 m beamline with long vacuum sections as shown in Fig. 1. In addition to the energy degradation due to vacuum windows and beam instrumentation, the device under test (DUT) position in the CHARM experimental area is located about 30 m away from the last vacuum exit window, causing a significant additional degradation of the beam energy and also some energy spreading of the initially mono-chromatic ion beam. The primary energy of the ion beam is thus reduced to the 0.220-2.39 GeV/n energy range. This results in LETs at the DUT position between 10.25 and 22.30 MeV/(mg/cm²) with range in Silicon between 5.79 and 167.11 mm for the highest and lowest LET, respectively. At the lowest extracted energy from the PS, 0.65 GeV/n, the amount of energy degradation and spread is the most severe and can therefore be taken as upper limits. The resulting beam energy at the DUT is 0.22 GeV/n with an FWHM spread of 14 MeV/n. The resulting LET and FWHM spread are 21.74 and 0.66 MeV/(mg/cm²). Currently, these energy, LET and range values of the ion beam are determined by means of FLUKA [6–8] Monte Carlo simulations that take into account the entire beam line material budget as shown schematically in Fig. 1 and summarized for all test configurations in Tab. I.

The LET range can be further extended by means of a remotely-controlled degradation system that allows inserting in the beam PMMA slabs of various thickness. This degrader is placed just in front of the DUT and the degrader thickness can be varied from 0.5 to almost 78 mm. This can allow extending the LET range up to > 40 MeV/(mg/cm²) while ensuring a

range in silicon $> 400 \mu\text{m}$. Nevertheless, the long air section and the degrader induce a rather large energy spread on the ion beam, that also results in a non-negligible spread of the ion LET. Both the primary beam energy and the degraded energy tuning can be achieved in less than one minute if pre-prepared and pre-calibrated.

Given the synchrotron acceleration, the ion beam is delivered to the DUTs in spills of 350 ms that are slowly extracted from the PS (i.e., in many turns). Therefore, the beam intensity is defined in terms of a fluence per spill, and measured in ions/cm²/spill. The total fluence during a test is obtained by summing up the fluence for each of the spills. The beam intensity range that was accessible to the users during the October 2023 test campaign was in the order of 500 to 10^5 ions/cm²/spill, which would correspond to average fluxes during the spill that are 1500 and 3×10^5 ions/cm²/s. This flux is in line with the requirements needed for radiation effects in electronics testing [9]. The spill duty-cycle is variable, but typically one can receive 3-5 spills per minute when running in parallel to the other PS users. The beam intensity can be changed over the full range in a few tens of seconds and, in the future, it will be made fully controllable to the users.

The beam intensity is measured on a spill-by-spill basis by a secondary emission chamber (SEC) that is always in the beam. This SEC is placed just after the beam vacuum exit window, which means that it is placed about 30 m before the DUT. For this reason, this instrument was calibrated by means of a silicon diode placed at the DUT position. The diode is capable of resolving the ion spill on an ion-by-ion basis and can thus provide an absolute measurement of the flux.

Finally, the ion beam has a Gaussian shape in both horizontal and vertical directions. During the October 2023 run, the beam size that was used was typically of the order of 10 cm full width at half maximum (FWHM) in both directions. These enabled the testing of several DUTs in parallel (for instance for the power MOSFETs) that were placed within the same 2 cm diameter. The beam size at the DUT position is measured with a multi-wire proportional chamber (MWPC) which is placed just behind the DUT position and it is in the beam at all time. In addition, the degrader system is also equipped with collimators with sizes of 5×5 and 10×10 cm² that allow removing the beam from the nearby electronics used to control the DUT. A remotely-controlled movable table also allows centering the DUT to the beam. The table can host several setup in parallel and move of 12 cm in both horizontal and vertical directions.

Note that, differently from the mixed-field CHARM facility, operation with the ion beam allows installing control electronics (e.g., power supplies, oscilloscopes, data acquisition systems, etc.) at just a couple of meters distance from the DUT with direct connection and no need to go through the patch panel. Nevertheless, due to the residual activation of the facility from the year-long mixed-field operation, the access to the facility remains restricted and typically no more than 3 accesses per day to the irradiation area were possible during working hours.

The different energy beam configurations used for the

different devices under test can be found in the Table I.

TABLE I
BEAM ENERGY CONFIGURATIONS USED IN THE SEE TESTS.

Extraction energy [MeV/n]	Degrader PMMA thickness [mm]	Energy@DUT [MeV/n]	LET@DUT [MeV·cm ² /mg]
2000	0	1690	10.25
1500	0	1170	10.75
1250	0	910	11.75
1000	0	650	13.57
1000	10	558	14.32
1000	20	450	15.61
1000	30	331	18.04
1000	34	279	19.78
1000	38	220	22.65
1000	40	173	24.98
1000	40.5	164	25.73
1000	41	155	26.59
1000	41.5	146	27.57
1000	42	136	28.70
1000	42.5	125	30.05
1000	43	114	31.68
1000	43.5	103	33.73
1000	44	90	36.42
1000	44.5	76	40.23
1000	45	59	46.03
900	0	530	14.25
850	0	470	15.20
800	0	410	16.25
750	0	350	17.57
750	10	226	22.27
750	12	194	24.43
750	14	159	27.78
750	16	120	34.20
750	18	36	59.74
700	0	290	18.8
650	0	220	21.74
650	2	183	24.26
650	4	146	27.50
650	6	111	33.56
650	7	85	39.90

III. DOSIMETRY

As previously introduced, the intensity characterization relied on Canberra FD 50-14-300 RM silicon detector [14], and it was performed analogously to the past studies [5]. This detector type is widely used for beam characterization [15, 16].

The detector was used to retrieve a calibration factor for a SEC instrument, that is permanently installed in the beamline, however features the absolute calibration only for 24 GeV proton beam. For this reason, several spills of varying beam intensities were extracted and the response of the SEC was measured in relation to the number of events measured in the silicon detector. Thanks to the spectroscopic nature of silicon detector measurements, only events induced by a primary beam were considered. An example for the case of 1 GeV/u extracted beam is depicted in Fig. 2, where the region induced by a direct ionization from the primary beam is highlighted. The related SEC response, presented in Fig. 3, is highly linear.

Due energy-dependent transmission throughout the beamline, the calibrations have been retrieved for all considered extraction energies. Moreover, introducing the degraders leads to additional beam fragmentation due to inelastic interactions in the PMMA. Therefore, for several thicknesses the transmission of the primary ions was measured, and applied on top of the aforementioned calibration. An example for the beam of 1 GeV/u (extracted energy) is depicted in Fig. 4. The cutoff around 45-47mm is because the primary beam is almost

Fig. 1. Schematic of the T08 beam line in the PS East Area at CERN, including the experimental facilities IRRAD and CHARM where the DUT position is located. The different beam line elements are shown with exception of the vacuum windows which are located at the extremities of each air section.

Fig. 2. Measured deposited energy in the silicon detector with a highlighted region corresponding to the events induced by a direct ionization by the primary beam (1 GeV/u at the extraction).

Fig. 3. Flux measured by a silicon detector as a function of SEC response. The slope of the linear fit is the SEC calibration factor for 1 GeV/u extracted beam.

entirely stopped in the PMMA through Coulomb interactions, and the energy depositions in silicon diode are induced by fragments.

IV. SEU MEASUREMENTS

SEU measurements were performed on the devices listed in Table II. The test conditions were as follows. All devices

Fig. 4. Transmission of the primary beam through the different total thicknesses of the PMMA, calculated as a ratio of a SEC calibration for a given configuration divided by the SEC calibration factor for non-degraded case.

were biased at 3.3 V, tested at room temperature and with a checkerboard pattern. The memories were written before irradiation and then read every 2.5 seconds, which allowed resolving single spills. After the read operation and error accumulation, if errors were found, the addresses in error were rewritten to the original pattern. Even if not really needed, the ISSI and Cypress static random access memories (SRAMs) were delidded, whereas the Renesas SRAM was not. The LETs reported for the Renesas are not taking into account the package thickness (which is not known at this time) for coherence with previous publications. In addition, the embedded error correction code (ECC) in the Cypress was disabled.

TABLE II
DEVICES UNDER TEST FOR SEU MEASUREMENTS.

Manufacturer	Reference	Date code	Size	Technology
ISSI	IS61WV204816BLL-10TLI	1650	32 Mbits	40 nm
Cypress	CY62167GE30-45ZXI	1731	16 Mbits	65 nm
Renesas	RMLV0816BGSA-4S2	9062	8 Mbits	110 nm

The beam conditions tested and reported here refer to primary beam tuning, between 650 MeV/n and 2 GeV/n, and to degraded runs with primary energy of 750 MeV/n and 1 GeV/n and degrader thickness between 10 and 45 mm. In some cases, runs at same energy were repeated over different days to also verify the repeatability of the beam conditions or of different beam conditions (e.g., same energy, but different ion fluence per spill).

The data are reported with error bars with 95% confidence

Fig. 5. SEU measurements on the ISSI SRAM collected at HEARTS@CERN with primary and degraded energies from the beam, comparison with data collected elsewhere. Weibull parameters: $LET_0 = 0.2 \text{ MeV}/(\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2)$, $\sigma_{sat} = 1.2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2/\text{bit}$, $W = 500$, $s = 1$.

Fig. 6. SEU measurements on the Cypress SRAM collected at HEARTS@CERN with primary and degraded energies from the beam, comparison with data collected elsewhere. Weibull parameters: $LET_0 = 0.1 \text{ MeV}/(\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2)$, $\sigma_{sat} = 2.6 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2/\text{bit}$, $W = 70$, $s = 1.2$.

Fig. 7. SEU measurements on the Renesas SRAM collected at HEARTS@CERN with primary and degraded energies from the beam, comparison with data collected elsewhere. Weibull parameters: $LET_0 = 13 \text{ MeV}/(\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2)$, $\sigma_{sat} = 2.5 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2/\text{bit}$, $W = 20$, $s = 3.3$.

level on the vertical axis that account for a 10% uncertainty on the beam fluence. The compiled data are reported for the three SRAMs in Figs. 5, 6, 7. Tabular data are also available at the end of the paper, see Tables V, VI, VII.

Each figure reports the data for all the runs performed at HEARTS@CERN subdivided on the type of beam configuration: primary beam, degraded from 750 MeV/n or degraded from 1000 MeV/n. Other than the HEARTS@CERN, the figures report also some data-points from other heavy ion facilities, either low or high-energy. The figures also report the Weibull fitting that was obtained based on the data measured elsewhere for ISSI and Cypress. For the Renesas, the Weibull was obtained trying to fit GSI and HEARTS@CERN data. However, the spread is higher and the fit is not optimal. Note also that the Renesas was tested with package, whose thickness is not known. So, both the GSI and HEARTS@CERN data-points would have to be shifted towards slightly to moderately higher LETs.

The ISSI and Cypress SRAMs are known to have extremely low LET thresholds [10, 11] and to have rather flat SEU cross sections above 10 MeV/(mg/cm²). On the other hand, the Renesas SRAM is a device for which no previous data were available. The possibility of varying the LET at steps of 1 MeV/(mg/cm²) by simple beam tuning allowed finding the LET threshold for this memory, which is set at 13 MeV/(mg/cm²). Below this energy, the SEU cross section is likely dominated by ion nuclear events. The agreement obtained for the ISSI and Cypress SRAM, for which numerous data-points measured elsewhere are available, is excellent for both primary energy and degraded energy beams at HEARTS@CERN.

V. SEL MEASUREMENTS

The devices used for the SEL measurements can be found in Table III. The samples were irradiated at room temperature, under normal irradiation and biased at 3.3 V. No specific pattern was written in the memories. All of the samples kept their original packaging. Following the SEL detection, the SEL hold-time was 1 ms after which 5 ms off-time was applied to the sample for power cycling. The maximum allowed current, used to identify a latch-up, was set to 100 mA, while the stand-by consumption of the memories was few mA.

TABLE III
DEVICES UNDER TEST FOR SEL MEASUREMENTS.

Manufacturer	Reference	Date code	Size [Mbit]	Technology [nm]
ISSI	IS61LV5128AL	–	16	180
Cypress	CY7C1069AV33	–	4	180
Samsung	K6R4016V1D	922	4	180

The results of the SEL measurements can be found in Fig. 9 where the experimental points feature error bars accounting for 10% uncertainty in the beam fluence and 95% confidence level in the SEL statistics. The values shown are a combination of primary beam energies and degraded beam energies. All of the LET values below or equal to 22.2 MeV·cm²/mg belong to facility primary energies while those higher are obtained by means of different degrader thicknesses (2, 4, 6 and 7 mm PMMA).

The ISSI cross-section is almost saturated for every LET value given its low threshold found in [12]. A proper cross-section curve can be seen for the Cypress and Samsung memories. In particular, the Samsung memory threshold is

approximately $12 \text{ MeV}\cdot\text{cm}^2/\text{mg}$, being the cross-section dominated by ion nuclear events.

Fig. 8. SEL measurements on memory devices collected at HEARTS@CERN.

Fig. 9. SEL measurements on memory devices collected at HEARTS@CERN compared to results in other standard-energy heavy ion facilities: RADEF and UCL.

VI. SEB MEASUREMENTS

The transistors used for the SEB measurements can be found in Table IV. The devices were tested at room temperature and at normal incidence. The devices were biased in off-mode with the gate grounded while the drain voltage was kept constant, and only varied among different runs. The overall setup is equivalent to the one showed in [13]. Moreover, it featured $1 \text{ M}\Omega$ shunt resistor and 100 pF decoupling capacitors in series with a $1 \text{ k}\Omega$ series resistor for every sample. All of the samples kept their original packaging.

TABLE IV
DEVICES UNDER TEST FOR SEB MEASUREMENTS.

Manufacturer	Reference	Date code	Vmax [V]	I _{max} [A]
Infineon	IRFR4105ZPbF	P548G-1N-UC	55	30
STMicroelectronics	STD10NF10T4	GF105629	100	13

The results of the SEB measurements can be found in Figs. 10, 11, 12 and 13 where the experimental points feature error bars accounting for 10% uncertainty in the beam fluence and 95% confidence level in the SEB statistics. For

this measurement, all of the LET values below or equal to $22.2 \text{ MeV}\cdot\text{cm}^2/\text{mg}$ belong to facility primary energies while the higher LET values are obtained by means of different degrader thicknesses (2 and 4 mm PMMA).

Fig. 10. SEB measurements on IRFR4105ZPbF collected at HEARTS@CERN as a function of the drain bias voltage.

Figures 10 and 12 show the SEB cross-section dependency as a function of the drain voltage for different LET values. As the beam LET increases, the threshold voltage to induce SEBs decreases, while the cross-section slope increases, reaching much quickly the saturation values. If the same data is plotted as a function of the LET and a parametric variation of the drain voltage (Figs. 11 and 13) the role of the voltage becomes key. For higher voltages, the cross-section saturation value increases, while the LET threshold becomes smaller.

Fig. 11. SEB measurements on IRFR4105ZPbF collected at HEARTS@CERN as a function of the LET.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The paper reports on SEE measurements (SEU, SEL, SEB) performed on a number of devices in the new HEART@CERN

Fig. 12. SEB measurements on STD10NF10T4 collected at HEARTS@CERN as a function of the drain bias voltage.

Fig. 13. SEB measurements on STD10NF10T4 collected at HEARTS@CERN as a function of the LET.

high-energy heavy ion facility at CERN. These ions have shown their capability to induce SEEs in a variety of EEE parts regardless of their packaging.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Mekki, M. Brugger, R. Garcia Alia, A. Thornton, N. C. Dos Santos Mota, and S. Danzeca, "CHARM: a mixed field facility at CERN for radiation test in ground, atmospheric, space and accelerator representative environments," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 2106-2114, Aug. 2016.
- [2] D. Prelipcean et al., "Benchmark between measured and simulated radiation level data at the mixed-field CHARM facility at CERN," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 69, no. 7, pp. 1557-1564, July 2022.
- [3] P. Fernandez-Martinez et al., "SEE tests with ultra energetic Xe ion beam in the CHARM facility at CERN," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 66, no. 7, pp. 1523-1531, July 2019.
- [4] M. Kastriotou et al., "Single event effect testing with ultrahigh energy heavy ion beams," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 63-70, Jan. 2020.

- [5] K. Bilko et al., "CHARM high-energy ions for micro electronics reliability assurance (CHIMERA)," *accepted for publication in IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*
- [6] G. Battistoni et al., "Overview of the FLUKA code," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 82, pp. 10-18, August 2015.
- [7] T.T. Bohlen et al., "The FLUKA Code: Developments and Challenges for High Energy and Medical Applications," *Nuclear Data Sheets*, vol. 120, pp. 211-214, June 2014.
- [8] C. Ahdida et al., "New capabilities of the FLUKA multi-purpose code," *Front. Phys.*, vol. 9, art. no. 788253, Jan. 2022.
- [9] ESCC 25100, "Single event effects test method and guidelines," European Space Components Coordination, ESA.
- [10] A. Coronetti et al., "Assessment of proton direct ionization for the radiation hardness assurance of deep sub-micron SRAMs used in space applications," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 937-948, May 2021.
- [11] A. Coronetti et al., "SEU characterization of commercial and custom-designed SRAMs based on 90-nm technology and below," in *IEEE Radiation Effects Data Workshop Rec.*, Santa Fe, NM, USA, Dec. 2020, pp. 56-63.
- [12] R. Harboe-Sorensen et al., "From the reference SEU monitor to the technology demonstration module on-board PROBA-II," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 3082-3087, Dec. 2008.
- [13] P. Fernández-Martínez et al., "SEE testing on commercial power MOS-FETs," 2020 20th European Conference on Radiation and Its Effects on Components and Systems (RADECS), Toulouse, France, 2020, pp. 178-185.
- [14] K. Bilko, "Canberra PIPS detector FD 50-14-300 RM (aka Vanessa II): performance data," online, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.10973056
- [15] K. Bilko et al., "Mixed-Field Radiation Monitoring and Beam Characterization Through Silicon Diode Detectors," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 777-784, April 2024.
- [16] A. Waets et al., "Very-High-Energy Heavy Ion Beam Dosimetry using Solid State Detectors for Electronics Testing" *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, accepted for publication.

TABLE V
EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR THE ISSI SRAM AS COLLECTED AT HEARTS@CERN.

LET (MeV/(mg/cm ²))	Fluence (ions/cm ²)	SEU	SEU cross section (cm ² /bit)
21.75	1.19 × 10 ⁶	219472	(5.51 ± 1.10) × 10 ⁻⁹
17.57	5.95 × 10 ⁵	57209	(2.87 ± 0.58) × 10 ⁻⁹
17.57	3.38 × 10 ⁵	34020	(3.00 ± 0.60) × 10 ⁻⁹
17.57	2.29 × 10 ⁵	22854	(2.97 ± 0.59) × 10 ⁻⁹
17.57	2.07 × 10 ⁵	20222	(2.91 ± 0.58) × 10 ⁻⁹
17.57	3.40 × 10 ⁵	32514	(2.85 ± 0.57) × 10 ⁻⁹
17.57	2.42 × 10 ⁵	22698	(2.79 ± 0.56) × 10 ⁻⁹
22.27	3.38 × 10 ⁵	39032	(3.44 ± 0.69) × 10 ⁻⁹
24.43	3.26 × 10 ⁵	53720	(4.91 ± 0.98) × 10 ⁻⁹
27.78	3.01 × 10 ⁵	54825	(5.43 ± 1.09) × 10 ⁻⁹
34.20	2.36 × 10 ⁵	51198	(6.47 ± 1.29) × 10 ⁻⁹
59.74	1.15 × 10 ⁵	37205	(9.68 ± 1.94) × 10 ⁻⁹
13.58	1.74 × 10 ⁶	132070	(2.26 ± 0.45) × 10 ⁻⁹
14.32	1.00 × 10 ⁶	86501	(2.57 ± 0.52) × 10 ⁻⁹
15.61	8.46 × 10 ⁵	82835	(2.92 ± 0.58) × 10 ⁻⁹
18.04	8.50 × 10 ⁵	99827	(3.50 ± 0.70) × 10 ⁻⁹
19.78	7.35 × 10 ⁵	106446	(4.31 ± 0.86) × 10 ⁻⁹
22.65	6.72 × 10 ⁵	120257	(5.33 ± 1.07) × 10 ⁻⁹
24.98	5.56 × 10 ⁵	143927	(7.72 ± 1.54) × 10 ⁻⁹
25.73	4.77 × 10 ⁵	127982	(8.00 ± 1.60) × 10 ⁻⁹
26.59	3.77 × 10 ⁵	96535	(7.63 ± 1.53) × 10 ⁻⁹
27.57	5.76 × 10 ⁵	119734	(6.20 ± 1.24) × 10 ⁻⁹
28.70	5.80 × 10 ⁵	133623	(6.87 ± 1.37) × 10 ⁻⁹
30.05	5.47 × 10 ⁵	132673	(7.23 ± 1.45) × 10 ⁻⁹
31.68	3.86 × 10 ⁵	112067	(8.65 ± 1.73) × 10 ⁻⁹
33.73	4.15 × 10 ⁵	123006	(8.84 ± 1.77) × 10 ⁻⁹
36.42	3.58 × 10 ⁵	118903	(9.90 ± 1.98) × 10 ⁻⁹
40.23	2.54 × 10 ⁵	88850	(1.04 ± 2.08) × 10 ⁻⁸
46.03	1.83 × 10 ⁵	80184	(1.31 ± 2.61) × 10 ⁻⁸
13.58	9.20 × 10 ⁵	67409	(2.18 ± 0.44) × 10 ⁻⁹
13.58	6.37 × 10 ⁵	47802	(2.24 ± 0.45) × 10 ⁻⁹
13.58	7.76 × 10 ⁵	55719	(2.14 ± 0.43) × 10 ⁻⁹
13.58	7.68 × 10 ⁵	51920	(2.01 ± 0.40) × 10 ⁻⁹
13.58	7.58 × 10 ⁵	54382	(2.14 ± 0.43) × 10 ⁻⁹

TABLE VI
EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR THE CYPRESS SRAM AS COLLECTED AT
HEARTS@CERN.

LET (MeV/(mg/cm ²))	Fluence (ions/cm ²)	SEU	SEU cross section (cm ² /bit)
17.57	7.89×10^3	4267	$(3.23 \pm 0.65) \times 10^{-8}$
22.27	6.89×10^3	4543	$(3.93 \pm 0.79) \times 10^{-8}$
24.43	5.55×10^3	5534	$(5.94 \pm 1.19) \times 10^{-8}$
27.78	4.76×10^3	5493	$(6.87 \pm 1.37) \times 10^{-8}$
34.20	3.83×10^3	4528	$(7.99 \pm 1.60) \times 10^{-8}$
59.74	2.36×10^3	4639	$(1.17 \pm 0.24) \times 10^{-7}$
13.58	9.97×10^3	3977	$(2.38 \pm 0.48) \times 10^{-8}$
14.32	8.71×10^3	3774	$(2.58 \pm 0.52) \times 10^{-8}$
15.61	8.03×10^3	4386	$(3.26 \pm 0.65) \times 10^{-8}$
18.04	7.32×10^3	4494	$(3.66 \pm 0.73) \times 10^{-8}$
19.78	5.66×10^3	4216	$(4.44 \pm 0.89) \times 10^{-8}$
22.65	4.32×10^3	4271	$(5.89 \pm 1.18) \times 10^{-8}$
24.98	3.35×10^3	4901	$(8.73 \pm 1.75) \times 10^{-8}$
25.73	3.45×10^3	5438	$(9.40 \pm 1.88) \times 10^{-8}$
26.59	3.87×10^3	5171	$(7.97 \pm 1.59) \times 10^{-8}$
27.57	3.54×10^3	4759	$(8.02 \pm 1.60) \times 10^{-8}$
28.70	3.08×10^3	3967	$(7.68 \pm 1.54) \times 10^{-8}$
30.05	3.31×10^3	4566	$(8.21 \pm 1.64) \times 10^{-8}$
31.68	2.74×10^3	4127	$(8.96 \pm 1.79) \times 10^{-8}$
33.73	2.01×10^3	3146	$(9.32 \pm 1.86) \times 10^{-8}$
36.42	1.95×10^3	3597	$(1.10 \pm 0.22) \times 10^{-7}$
40.23	1.34×10^3	2963	$(1.31 \pm 0.26) \times 10^{-7}$
46.03	9.73×10^2	2711	$(1.66 \pm 0.33) \times 10^{-7}$
21.75	3.95×10^3	3163	$(4.78 \pm 0.96) \times 10^{-8}$
16.25	6.90×10^3	3635	$(3.14 \pm 0.63) \times 10^{-8}$
13.64	3.61×10^3	1704	$(2.81 \pm 0.56) \times 10^{-8}$
12.20	4.52×10^3	1801	$(2.37 \pm 0.48) \times 10^{-8}$
11.41	3.31×10^3	1258	$(2.27 \pm 0.45) \times 10^{-8}$
10.97	1.93×10^3	706	$(2.19 \pm 0.44) \times 10^{-8}$
10.73	3.40×10^2	118	$(2.07 \pm 0.42) \times 10^{-8}$
21.75	2.94×10^3	3044	$(6.17 \pm 1.23) \times 10^{-8}$
21.75	6.69×10^4	67640	$(6.03 \pm 1.21) \times 10^{-8}$

TABLE VII
EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR THE RENESAS SRAM AS COLLECTED AT
HEARTS@CERN.

LET (MeV/(mg/cm ²))	Fluence (ions/cm ²)	SEU	SEU cross section (cm ² /bit)
13.58	2.61×10^6	6	$(2.47 \pm 1.90) \times 10^{-13}$
14.32	2.35×10^6	3	$(1.52 \pm 2.05) \times 10^{-13}$
15.61	2.27×10^6	27	$(1.42 \pm 0.35) \times 10^{-12}$
18.04	1.94×10^6	233	$(1.43 \pm 0.29) \times 10^{-11}$
19.78	1.05×10^6	637	$(7.25 \pm 1.45) \times 10^{-11}$
22.65	9.33×10^5	2746	$(3.51 \pm 0.70) \times 10^{-10}$
25.73	5.33×10^5	6070	$(1.36 \pm 0.27) \times 10^{-9}$
26.59	3.80×10^5	4500	$(1.41 \pm 0.28) \times 10^{-9}$
27.57	5.08×10^5	4110	$(9.65 \pm 1.93) \times 10^{-10}$
28.70	4.21×10^5	4778	$(1.35 \pm 0.27) \times 10^{-9}$
30.05	2.93×10^5	4235	$(1.73 \pm 0.35) \times 10^{-9}$
31.68	3.16×10^5	5709	$(2.16 \pm 0.43) \times 10^{-9}$
33.73	2.56×10^5	5171	$(2.41 \pm 0.48) \times 10^{-9}$
36.42	1.82×10^5	4490	$(2.94 \pm 0.59) \times 10^{-9}$
40.23	1.40×10^5	3585	$(3.06 \pm 0.61) \times 10^{-9}$
46.03	9.59×10^4	2593	$(3.22 \pm 0.65) \times 10^{-9}$
17.57	1.17×10^6	88	$(8.94 \pm 1.83) \times 10^{-12}$
22.27	4.66×10^5	713	$(1.82 \pm 0.37) \times 10^{-10}$
24.43	2.59×10^5	1086	$(4.99 \pm 1.00) \times 10^{-10}$
27.78	2.39×10^5	2055	$(1.03 \pm 0.21) \times 10^{-9}$
34.20	2.58×10^5	3123	$(1.44 \pm 0.29) \times 10^{-9}$
59.74	8.37×10^5	2081	$(2.96 \pm 0.59) \times 10^{-9}$
13.58	6.55×10^7	85	$(1.55 \pm 0.32) \times 10^{-13}$
21.75	7.03×10^5	2257	$(3.83 \pm 0.77) \times 10^{-10}$
16.25	7.25×10^6	272	$(4.47 \pm 0.90) \times 10^{-12}$
15.20	2.33×10^7	160	$(8.18 \pm 1.65) \times 10^{-13}$
13.98	4.63×10^7	106	$(2.73 \pm 0.55) \times 10^{-13}$
11.62	2.79×10^7	101	$(4.21 \pm 0.88) \times 10^{-13}$

TABLE VIII
EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR THE IS61LV5128AL SRAM MEMORY AS
COLLECTED AT HEARTS@CERN.

LET [MeV·cm ² /mg]	Fluence [ion/cm ²]	SEL	Cross-section [cm ²]
10.3	$2.5 \cdot 10^3$	58	$2.3^{+0.7}_{-0.6} \cdot 10^{-2}$
11.8	$3.7 \cdot 10^3$	127	$3.4^{+0.8}_{-0.7} \cdot 10^{-2}$
13.6	$6.8 \cdot 10^3$	287	$4.2^{+0.7}_{-0.7} \cdot 10^{-2}$
14.3	$9.6 \cdot 10^3$	575	$6.0^{+0.8}_{-0.8} \cdot 10^{-2}$
16.3	$6.7 \cdot 10^3$	519	$7.7^{+1.1}_{-1.1} \cdot 10^{-2}$
18.8	$4.3 \cdot 10^3$	556	$1.3^{+0.2}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-2}$
21.7	$4.0 \cdot 10^3$	414	$1.4^{+0.2}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-1}$
24.3	$3.9 \cdot 10^3$	425	$1.5^{+0.2}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-1}$
27.5	$3.6 \cdot 10^3$	357	$1.3^{+0.2}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-1}$
33.6	$3.6 \cdot 10^3$	320	$1.1^{+0.2}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-1}$
39.9	$6.5 \cdot 10^3$	485	$9.1^{+1.2}_{-1.2} \cdot 10^{-2}$

TABLE IX
EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR THE CY7C1069AV33 SRAM MEMORY AS
COLLECTED AT HEARTS@CERN.

LET [MeV·cm ² /mg]	Fluence [ion/cm ²]	SEL	Cross-section [cm ²]
10.3	$1.9 \cdot 10^5$	26	$1.3^{+0.7}_{-0.5} \cdot 10^{-4}$
11.8	$3.3 \cdot 10^5$	629	$1.9^{+0.3}_{-0.3} \cdot 10^{-3}$
13.6	$6.3 \cdot 10^3$	131	$2.1^{+0.5}_{-0.4} \cdot 10^{-2}$
14.3	$6.4 \cdot 10^3$	345	$5.4^{+0.8}_{-0.8} \cdot 10^{-2}$
16.3	$3.7 \cdot 10^3$	617	$1.7^{+0.3}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-1}$
18.8	$2.5 \cdot 10^3$	975	$3.9^{+0.6}_{-0.5} \cdot 10^{-1}$
21.7	$2.2 \cdot 10^3$	1152	$5.2^{+0.7}_{-0.7} \cdot 10^{-1}$
24.3	$2.0 \cdot 10^3$	928	$4.6^{+0.6}_{-0.6} \cdot 10^{-1}$
27.5	$1.7 \cdot 10^3$	862	$5.0^{+0.7}_{-0.7} \cdot 10^{-1}$
33.6	$3.2 \cdot 10^3$	1113	$3.5^{+0.5}_{-0.5} \cdot 10^{-1}$
39.9	$2.7 \cdot 10^3$	705	$2.6^{+0.4}_{-0.4} \cdot 10^{-1}$

TABLE X
EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR THE K6R4016V1D SRAM MEMORY AS
COLLECTED AT HEARTS@CERN.

LET [MeV·cm ² /mg]	Fluence [ion/cm ²]	SEL	Cross-section [cm ²]
10.3	$1.4 \cdot 10^8$	957	$6.7^{+0.8}_{-0.8} \cdot 10^{-6}$
10.8	$2.3 \cdot 10^8$	1042	$4.5^{+0.5}_{-0.5} \cdot 10^{-6}$
11.8	$3.7 \cdot 10^7$	446	$1.2^{+0.2}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-5}$
13.6	$1.7 \cdot 10^7$	98	$5.7^{+1.4}_{-1.2} \cdot 10^{-6}$
14.3	$1.1 \cdot 10^7$	87	$8.3^{+2.1}_{-1.9} \cdot 10^{-6}$
15.2	$2.4 \cdot 10^7$	303	$1.3^{+0.2}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-5}$
16.3	$3.2 \cdot 10^6$	269	$8.5^{+1.4}_{-1.3} \cdot 10^{-5}$
17.6	$2.7 \cdot 10^6$	449	$1.7^{+0.2}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-4}$
18.8	$1.4 \cdot 10^5$	477	$3.3^{+0.5}_{-0.5} \cdot 10^{-3}$
21.7	$4.1 \cdot 10^4$	750	$1.8^{+0.2}_{-0.2} \cdot 10^{-2}$
24.3	$2.8 \cdot 10^4$	585	$2.1^{+0.3}_{-0.3} \cdot 10^{-2}$
27.5	$2.6 \cdot 10^4$	1124	$4.3^{+0.5}_{-0.5} \cdot 10^{-2}$
33.6	$2.3 \cdot 10^4$	1047	$4.5^{+0.6}_{-0.6} \cdot 10^{-2}$
39.9	$2.7 \cdot 10^4$	1198	$4.5^{+0.5}_{-0.5} \cdot 10^{-2}$

TABLE XI
EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR THE IRFR4105ZPbF POWER MOSFET AS
COLLECTED AT HEARTS@CERN.

LET [MeV·cm ² /mg]	Voltage [V]	Fluence [ion/cm ²]	Samples	SEB	Cross-section [cm ²]
10.3	45	1.6·10 ⁶	5	7	8.8 ^{+9.3} _{-5.3} ·10 ⁻⁷
10.3	50	1.8·10 ⁶	4	24	3.4 ^{+1.7} _{-1.2} ·10 ⁻⁶
10.3	55	2.4·10 ⁶	4	73	7.6 ^{+2.1} _{-1.8} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	35	2.6·10 ⁶	7	6	3.3 ^{+3.2} _{-2.1} ·10 ⁻⁷
13.3	40	2.4·10 ⁶	7	24	1.4 ^{+0.7} _{-0.5} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	45	2.2·10 ⁶	7	26	1.7 ^{+0.8} _{-0.6} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	50	4.3·10 ⁶	4	89	5.2 ^{+1.1} _{-0.8} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	55	1.2·10 ⁶	4	3882	8.1 ^{+0.8} _{-0.8} ·10 ⁻⁴
15.2	35	2.2·10 ⁶	7	15	9.7 ^{+6.4} _{-4.4} ·10 ⁻⁷
15.2	40	2.2·10 ⁶	7	59	3.8 ^{+1.2} _{-1.0} ·10 ⁻⁶
15.2	45	1.5·10 ⁶	7	177	1.7 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁵
15.2	50	6.7·10 ⁵	7	1056	2.3 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻⁴
17.6	30	1.8·10 ⁶	7	21	1.7 ^{+0.9} _{-0.7} ·10 ⁻⁶
17.6	35	1.1·10 ⁶	7	92	1.2 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁵
17.6	40	6.3·10 ⁵	7	504	1.1 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻⁴
17.6	45	1.9·10 ⁵	7	767	5.8 ^{+0.7} _{-0.7} ·10 ⁻⁴
22.3	25	1.2·10 ⁶	6	43	6.0 ^{+0.1} _{-1.8} ·10 ⁻⁶
22.3	30	7.5·10 ⁵	6	1234	2.7 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁴
22.3	35	3.1·10 ⁵	6	2249	1.2 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1} ·10 ⁻³
22.3	40	1.6·10 ⁵	6	2291	2.4 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻³
26.3	20	7.9·10 ⁵	6	66	1.4 ^{+0.4} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁵
26.3	25	8.6·10 ⁵	6	2014	3.9 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4} ·10 ⁻⁴
26.3	30	3.7·10 ⁵	6	2495	1.1 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1} ·10 ⁻³
26.3	35	3.8·10 ⁵	6	4782	2.1 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻³
26.3	40	1.4·10 ⁵	5	3250	4.6 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5} ·10 ⁻³
31.3	25	7.5·10 ⁵	5	1030	2.8 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁴
31.3	30	4.7·10 ⁵	5	2295	9.8 ^{+1.1} _{-1.1} ·10 ⁻⁴
31.3	35	5.7·10 ⁵	5	5932	2.1 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻³
31.3	40	2.4·10 ⁵	5	5474	4.6 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5} ·10 ⁻³

TABLE XII
EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR THE STD10NF10T4 POWER MOSFET AS
COLLECTED AT HEARTS@CERN.

LET [MeV·cm ² /mg]	Voltage [V]	Fluence [ion/cm ²]	Samples	SEB	Cross-section [cm ²]
10.3	35	5.6·10 ⁶	7	19	4.9 ^{+2.8} _{-2.0} ·10 ⁻⁷
10.3	40	5.7·10 ⁶	7	35	8.8 ^{+2.8} _{-2.8} ·10 ⁻⁷
10.3	45	4.5·10 ⁶	7	26	8.3 ^{+4.0} _{-3.0} ·10 ⁻⁷
10.3	50	6.3·10 ⁶	7	50	1.1 ^{+0.4} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁶
10.3	55	4.6·10 ⁶	7	68	2.1 ^{+0.6} _{-0.5} ·10 ⁻⁶
10.3	60	2.1·10 ⁶	7	28	1.9 ^{+0.9} _{-0.7} ·10 ⁻⁶
10.3	65	3.2·10 ⁶	7	69	3.1 ^{+0.9} _{-0.8} ·10 ⁻⁶
10.3	70	4.2·10 ⁶	7	100	3.4 ^{+0.8} _{-0.7} ·10 ⁻⁶
10.3	75	4.1·10 ⁶	7	133	4.6 ^{+1.0} _{-0.9} ·10 ⁻⁶
11.8	35	5.9·10 ⁶	7	63	1.5 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4} ·10 ⁻⁶
11.8	40	4.1·10 ⁶	5	46	2.3 ^{+0.8} _{-0.6} ·10 ⁻⁶
11.8	45	3.9·10 ⁶	7	104	3.8 ^{+1.0} _{-0.8} ·10 ⁻⁶
11.8	50	4.2·10 ⁶	7	153	5.3 ^{+1.1} _{-1.0} ·10 ⁻⁶
11.8	55	3.9·10 ⁶	7	166	6.1 ^{+1.2} _{-1.1} ·10 ⁻⁶
11.8	60	3.6·10 ⁶	7	191	7.5 ^{+1.4} _{-1.3} ·10 ⁻⁶
11.8	65	3.9·10 ⁶	7	227	8.2 ^{+1.4} _{-1.3} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	30	7.0·10 ⁶	7	11	2.2 ^{+1.8} _{-1.8} ·10 ⁻⁷
13.3	35	5.2·10 ⁶	7	17	4.7 ^{+2.9} _{-2.0} ·10 ⁻⁷
13.3	40	3.9·10 ⁶	7	19	6.9 ^{+1.1} _{-1.0} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	45	3.3·10 ⁶	7	30	1.3 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	50	3.7·10 ⁶	7	50	1.9 ^{+0.6} _{-0.5} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	55	3.5·10 ⁶	7	56	2.3 ^{+0.7} _{-0.7} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	60	3.5·10 ⁶	7	99	4.0 ^{+1.0} _{-0.9} ·10 ⁻⁶
13.3	65	2.7·10 ⁶	7	98	5.3 ^{+1.3} _{-1.3} ·10 ⁻⁶
15.2	30	5.0·10 ⁶	7	57	1.6 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4} ·10 ⁻⁶
15.2	35	5.5·10 ⁶	7	128	3.3 ^{+0.7} _{-0.6} ·10 ⁻⁶
15.2	40	2.9·10 ⁶	7	135	6.7 ^{+1.4} _{-1.4} ·10 ⁻⁶
15.2	45	2.9·10 ⁶	7	183	9.1 ^{+1.7} _{-1.5} ·10 ⁻⁶
15.2	50	1.5·10 ⁶	7	181	1.7 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁵
15.2	55	1.5·10 ⁶	7	467	4.4 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6} ·10 ⁻⁵
15.2	60	6.6·10 ⁶	7	611	1.3 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻⁴
15.2	65	5.6·10 ⁶	7	1411	3.6 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4} ·10 ⁻⁴
15.2	70	5.7·10 ⁶	7	3316	8.4 ^{+0.9} _{-0.9} ·10 ⁻⁴
18.8	20	1.7·10 ⁶	7	2308	1.9 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻⁴
18.8	25	1.7·10 ⁶	7	3840	3.2 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁴
18.8	30	1.4·10 ⁶	7	2711	2.9 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁴
18.8	35	3.5·10 ⁵	7	1371	5.6 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6} ·10 ⁻⁴
18.8	40	3.8·10 ⁵	7	2777	1.0 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1} ·10 ⁻³
18.8	45	2.2·10 ⁵	7	2230	1.5 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻³
18.8	50	2.2·10 ⁵	7	3001	1.9 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻³
18.8	55	2.4·10 ⁵	7	4489	2.7 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻³
18.8	60	1.2·10 ⁵	7	2878	3.5 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4} ·10 ⁻³
22.3	20	6.4·10 ⁵	7	956	2.1 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻⁴
22.3	25	2.8·10 ⁵	7	1337	6.9 ^{+0.8} _{-0.8} ·10 ⁻⁴
22.3	30	2.2·10 ⁵	7	2262	1.5 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2} ·10 ⁻³
22.3	35	1.5·10 ⁵	7	2532	2.4 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3} ·10 ⁻³
22.3	40	1.2·10 ⁵	7	3162	3.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4} ·10 ⁻³
22.3	45	6.6·10 ⁴	7	1821	3.9 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4} ·10 ⁻³
22.3	50	1.2·10 ⁵	7	4617	5.5 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6} ·10 ⁻³
22.3	55	1.1·10 ⁵	7	5198	6.8 ^{+0.7} _{-0.7} ·10 ⁻³
22.3	60	1.2·10 ⁵	7	7804	9.3 ^{+1.0} _{-1.0} ·10 ⁻³